

The Impact of Organizational Learning on Achieving Administrative Excellence In Jordanian public sector

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Othman Hussein Al-Bataineh-Faculty Of Economic And Management Sciences Yarmouk Universiti Irbid, Jordan ⁽²⁾Dr. Rasheda Mohammad Ibrahim-Faculty Of Economic And Management Sciences Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin Terengganu, Malaysia ⁽³⁾Prof. Raed Ababneh-Faculty Of Economic And Management Sciences Yarmouk Universiti Irbid, Jordan

Abstract:

This study aims at finding out the scope of Organizational Learning. It also aims at recognizing the level of achieving the Administrative excellence dimensions at the Jordanian public sector. The findings show that there is a positive association between Organizational Learning (Personal empowerment , Systematic thinking , the mental patterns , participated vision , teamwork learning) and administrative excellence (Leadership excellence , Subordinates excellence , the structure excellence , the strategy excellence , culture excellence ,). In conclusion, the public sector should consider enhancing Organizational Learning to boost the level of Administrative excellence

Keywords: Organizational Learning , Administrative Excellence , Jordanian public sector.

Introduction

The organizations must be able to learn and innovate (Engeström 2018) so that these changes can be accompanied by the age of knowledge in order to adapt and develop in their environment. The pivotal theme of the learning age is the intensification of the intense interest in the man, the development and investment of his mental abilities and his being the basis for achieving any progress or development, and the central feature of science and scientific research as the basis for any work. Technical progress, cognitive explosion, and the information revolution have become the driving force and engine for the progress of organization towards development and progress throughout the world to become an educated organization (Bennet and Bennet 2004). The learning organization is characterized as an environment in which efforts to share creative knowledge and creative ideas are intertwined thanks to the development of the information and communications revolution. The gradual transition from the industrial age to the learning age has emerged in the context of accelerated globalization, interactive environments, influence, and information exchange. In the current period, there has been increasing interest in the Organization, which learns from itself and from other organizations to reveal their best practices and to move the knowledge quickly and effectively throughout their entity in a participatory manner in order to survive in the changing circumstances they face. Singla, Sethi et al. (2018) argued no organization can achieve perfection and perfection because learning is a continuous and renewable process, so researchers and practitioners have begun to focus on the concept of an educated organization, bearing in mind the many principles and values that call on these organizations

to adopt creative and modern thinking patterns. The change in the prevailing culture requires the acceleration of administrative change processes to get rid of the prevailing bureaucracy, and the decentralization and delegation of powers with the accompanying training sufficient to ensure the success of the mission to enrich the culture of learning and growth and excellence. The role of organizational learning is central to excellence, innovation, and creativity within any organization (Archer-Brown and Kietzmann 2018). Organizations need ways and means to identify the obstacles they face, their need for a means of gathering information that enables them to make good decisions, and the need for continuous development of their members, whether managers or employees. Only as a product of organizational excellence and creativity.

Therefore, the present study seeks to identify the impact of organizational learning on its basic dimensions (personal empowerment, systemic thinking, mental models, participated vision, and teamwork learning) in achieving administrative excellence (Leadership excellence , Subordinates excellence , the structure excellence , the strategy excellence , culture excellence , providing services excellence).

AIMS OF THE STUDY:

The study attempts to achieve the following objectives:

1. The extent to which organizational learning practice (personal empowerment, systemic thinking, mental models, shared vision, and team learning) is explored in the Jordanian public sector from the point of view of its employees.
2. Recognition of the level of achieving the dimensions of administrative excellence (excellence of leadership, the excellence of subordinates, distinguished structure, the excellence of strategy, the excellence of culture and excellence of services) in the Jordanian public sector from the point of view of its employees.
3. To recognize the impact of the practice of organizational learning in achieving administrative excellence in the Jordanian public sector.
4. Making suggestions and recommendations on how to activate the role of organizational learning in achieving administrative excellence in the Jordanian public sector and the possibility of circulating practical conclusions to other organizations in Jordan as much as possible.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Organizational Learning Concept

There are numerous and varied definitions of organizational learning according to the different studies studied by researchers (Ramadan, Dahiyat, et al. 2017), who are considered to be pioneers of organizational learning as a process of interest in the intellectual capital generated by the human element, And correct errors that have been detected. Daniel (2018) describes it as the process leading to better work through better learning and better understanding. Sannino and Engeström (2017) defines organizational learning as a collective phenomenon to acquire and develop competencies continuously and deeply with the aim of changing the mode of business management and changing the conditions. Archer-Brown and Kietzmann (2018) defined it as a dynamic process of creating, acquiring and disseminating knowledge with a view to developing human resource capacities, thus contributing effectively to the development of the Organization's performance. Archer-Brown and Kietzmann (2018) defined organizational learning as the organization's continued excellence in global best practices in its performance, connecting its clients and clients with the relationships of support and interaction, and recognizing the capabilities of its competitors, strengths, and weaknesses and the surrounding environment. As Dixon (2017) defines organizational learning as those organizations that possess a technological environment capable of implementing knowledge management in their management processes, they have an organizational culture that enables employees to achieve the strategic goals of the organization by exchanging ideas and information available to them.

In this regard, the researcher defines organizational learning as an ongoing process through which the organization seeks to invest effectively in the human resource competency of continuous learning, skill, and behaviors individually and collectively, thus enabling it to face the future in the context of creating an environment conducive to learning.

2. Administrative Excellence Concept:

Organizations strive to achieve excellence in all their businesses and achieve results that outperform their competitors and even themselves (Ross 2017). The administrative excellence is defined as "a positive and desirable situation that emphasizes that the organization works more efficiently and more efficiently than other organizations and in a manner that ensures that it is unique from its environment and product (Bryson 2018). Bryson (2018) defined administrative excellence as "the organizations' pursuit of opportunities, preceded by effective strategic planning, with a common vision of clarity of purpose, adequacy of resources, and keenness on performance. To contribute strategically through excellence in its performance and solve its problems and then achieve its objectives effectively distinguish them from other organizations As defined administrative excellence: the excellence that has been achieved by the institution towards the market in which it operates. administrative excellence is seen in terms of leadership excellence and excellence Subordinates, strategic excellence, organizational structure, organizational culture, and service excellence (Al Shobakib, Abu Amuna, et al. 2017). Additionally Organizations that are distinguished by a range of important characteristics (Bartlett and Ghoshal 2002).

1. Organizations have the ability to accept difficult business. Accepting hard work is one of the most important sources of managerial excellence, where opportunities for growth and rapid learning of

organizations, helping to improve processes and starting work from scratch. He also noted that efficient leadership in organizations serves as role models.

2 - have a prominent role in stimulating excellence and encouragement,

3. The ability of organizations to cope with difficulties and the commission of errors and the Organization's handling and response to crises contribute to the refinement and excellence of the Organization's decisions.

4 - Emphasis on the expertise away from work, distinguished organizations have expertise outside the scope of work, such as community service and provide many opportunities for him. While not neglecting training programs, where it turns out that what is learned directly from the training opportunities.

Conceptual framework

METHOD

1. Procedure

The study questionnaire was prepared and distributed to the study sample for the purpose of collecting the necessary field information on the subject of the study and then unloading it and analyzing it using the statistical program (SPSS) and using the appropriate statistical tests in order to reach the results of the study and to submit suggestions and recommendations accordingly. The researcher relied on previous literature from books, research, and studies that have a direct relationship in the field of research.

The study sample was selected according to the percentage of job representation (Director, Head of the department, Chief Division, Officer), in the studied society and in a randomized, stratified manner. The study tool was distributed in a relatively random manner to the members of the study sample from the administrative titles above. The total number of all employees reached (925), with the number of supervising posts (319) as manager, head of department and head of the division, and the number of non-supervisory posts reached (606). The researcher took a relatively random stratified sample of (35%) of the supervising supervisory positions according to the percentage of the total representation in the study society, which is equivalent to (112) leading employees, and (65%) of the non-supervisory posts according to the representation ratio which is equivalent to (394).

2. variable

Age was subdivided into four groups; Less than 30 years, 30-40 years old, 41 - 50 years old, 51 years old and over. Job category was divided into, technical/administrative, and unit leader (Director, Head of the department, Chief Division, Officer). years of: service less than 5 years, 5-10 years, 11-15 years, 16 years and above.

The dependent variable is administrative Excellence: is defined as The ability of organizations to contribute strategically through excellence in their performance and solve their problems and then achieve their objectives effectively distinguish them from the other organizations' and the excellence of leadership and subordinates and organizational structure in addition to its distinct culture and that affect the excellence of its services (Krpan 2018), and was measured administrative excellence with subdimensions by 29 items and were rated on a five-point response scale (Likert scale) These items were scored on a five-point response scale ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree..

Subdimensions of administrative excellence are Leadership excellence, The leader's ability to exploit organizational opportunities, provide development opportunities, and accept business in a way that helps the organization cope with turbulent processes and multiple crises (Holbeche 2018). Subordinates excellence, the degree of the organization's members' enthusiasm for excellence in the performance of the functions of the organization with intellectual abilities and distinct creative capabilities to help overcome the obstacles faced by the Organization (Daniel 2018). the structure excellence, the structural framework that links the parts of the organization, defines the relationships between the work, centers and sections, and the expected cooperation between the parts of the organization, and illustrates the lines of authority and responsibility in a manner that helps to perform various activities to achieve the desired goals (Bolman and Deal 2017). the strategy excellence: The degree to which the steps taken by the Organization to achieve its vision, mission and interaction are defined as a comprehensive, integrated and integrated plan that links the Organization's strengths with its strategic capacity to address environmental challenges (Bryson 2018). culture excellence: the degree of conformity of behavior and distinguishing values and beliefs of individuals in the organization, and includes the elements of openness, cooperation, trust, originality, tribal activity, independence and face problems (Heckscher, Bernier, et al. 2017).

The independent variable is Organizational learning is defined an ongoing process in which individuals work within organizations to increase their abilities and personal ability to achieve the results they desire, in which new and comprehensive mental models of systemic thinking are supported and encouraged, where teamwork and a shared vision of groups to learn from each other (Schein 2017), and was measured Organizational learning with subdimensions by 28 items and were rated on a five-point response scale (Likert scale) These items were scored on a five-point response scale ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. the subdimensions of Organizational learning are Personal empowerment , Systematic thinking , the mental patterns , participated vision , teamwork learning.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the data collected in this study. Several statistical methods were used to use the data obtained to achieve the objectives of the study. The following tests were performed:

1. Reliability Test: To verify the level of internal consistency of the study instrument as one of the indicators of its stability.

2. Descriptive Statistical Techniques: Statistical methods were used, such as Frequency Distribution, Percentages, and Mean. The items were classified according to the degree of importance according to their statistical averages. The deviation was also used Standard Deviation to measure the dispersion of responses on arithmetical averages.

3. T & F_Test: This test was used when comparing two independent samples based on the arithmetic mean so that the superiority of the practice of the group obtaining the upper mean was achieved.

4. The Pearson Coefficient of Correlation Test was used to determine the extent of a correlation between organizational learning and administrative excellence.

5 - regression analysis to measure the effect of the independent variable (organizational learning) on the dependent variable (administrative excellence).

RESULTS

Cronbach's alpha were all within acceptable limits for the organizational learning variables and the administrative excellence (α ranged between .79 and .97). The inter-correlation

Table 1. The coefficient of internal consistency

<i>Domains</i>	<i>consistency</i>
<i>Personal empowerment ,</i>	0,80
<i>Systematic thinking</i>	0,79
<i>, the mental patterns ,</i>	0,84
<i>participated vision</i>	0,89
<i>, teamwork learning.</i>	0,89
Organizational learning	0,95
<i>(Leadership excellence</i>	0,85
<i>, Subordinates excellence</i>	0,90
<i>, the structure excellence</i>	0,86
<i>, the strategy excellence</i>	0,89
<i>, culture excellence ,</i>	0,88
<i>services excellence).</i>	0,89
<i>administrative excellence</i>	0,97

Table 2. Pearson correlation coefficient of the relationship between the dimensions of organizational learning and managerial excellence

		Personal Empowerment	Systematic thinking	the mental patterns	participated vision	, teamwork learning.	Organizational learning
Leadership excellence	Coefficient of correlation Statistical significance the number	,541** ,000 388	,593** ,000 388	,622** ,000 388	,663** ,000 388	,626** ,000 388	,717** ,000 388
<i>, Subordinates excellence</i>	Coefficient of correlation	,473**	,547**	,522**	,575**	,511**	,619**
<i>the structure excellence</i>	Coefficient of correlation	,476**	,564**	,560**	,635**	,531**	,654**
<i>the strategy excellence</i>	Coefficient of correlation	,538**	,558**	,565**	,622**	,577**	,673**
<i>culture excellence</i>	Coefficient of correlation	,491**	,548**	,574**	,551**	,504**	,626**
<i>services excellence</i>	Coefficient of correlation	,521**	,581**	,558**	,599**	,549**	,661**
<i>administrative excellence</i>	Coefficient of correlation	,727**	,801**	,815**	,842**	,783**	,933**

Table 2 shows a statistically significant positive relationship between the dimensions of organizational learning and administrative excellence in the Greater Irbid Municipality. The correlation coefficient (933) was found to be positive, with a significant positive correlation between organizational learning as a whole and administrative excellence. The correlation coefficient values (619, 717).

A positive relationship was found between personal empowerment and administrative excellence as a whole, where the value of the correlation coefficient was (727). A positive correlation was found between personal empowerment as a whole and administrative excellence separately. The correlation coefficient values (473-541).

The correlation coefficient (801) was found to be statistically significant. There was also a positive relationship between systemic thinking as a whole and administrative excellence separately. The correlation coefficient values (539-581) .

The correlation between the mental models as a whole and the administrative excellence were found to be significant at each end. The correlation coefficient values (522, -222) .

The correlation between the common vision as a whole and the administrative excellence was found to be the same at each level. The correlation coefficient values (551, 663) .

The correlation coefficient (783) was found to be statistically significant. There was also a positive relationship between the learning of the team as a whole and the administrative excellence at each end. The correlation coefficient values (504-626) .

Discussion and conclusion

In this section, the researcher presents a detailed presentation of the results of the study, which aims to reveal the extent of the practice of organizational learning (personal empowerment, systemic thinking, mental models, shared vision, and team learning). Structure, the excellence of the strategy, the excellence of culture and excellence of services) in the Jordanian public sector from the point of view of its employees. The study also sought to know the role of the practice of organizational learning in achieving administrative excellence and identify the statistical differences in the level of practicing organizational learning and administrative excellence in the public sector The Jordanian mother is attributed to the personal and functional variables of the employees (gender, age, scientific qualification, nature of work, years of service, job title).

The study included a set of questions and hypotheses; the following is the presentation of the results related to them and the submission of some recommendations that it is hoped to work on the organizational learning institution to achieve administrative excellence.

1. The general level of the practice of organizational learning as a whole in the Jordanian public sector from the point of view of its employees was high and at a level of (3.80) on a scale of 5 points.

2. The general level of the organizational learning dimensions were all high and came in the following descending order: Personal Empowerment With an average of 3.96, mental models and an arithmetic mean (3.85), the team learned, with an average of (3.83) My account (3.74), systemic thinking and arithmetic mean (3.65).

3 - The general level of the practice of administrative excellence as a whole was high and at a level of account (3,69).

4- The general level of the dimensions of administrative excellence was high except for the distinction of subordinates, it came in a medium and descending order. "The strategy was characterized by an average of 3.70, characterized by culture with an average of 3.67; The structure is characterized by an average of (3.53). The command is characterized by an average of (3.51), the subordinates are characterized by an arithmetic average (3.49).

5 - The results showed a statistically positive relationship between the dimensions of organizational learning and administrative excellence, where the value of the correlation coefficient (933).

6 - The results showed a significant positive impact in organizational learning on the administrative excellence in the Greater Irbid Municipality from the point of view of the employees, where organizational learning explained the value of (871) of the variation in the practice of administrative excellence.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings of the study, the researcher recommends the following

1. The organizations should support the practice of self-development of employees through the dimensions of organizational learning, through the dissemination of knowledge and exchange among employees, and increase their skills and efficiency in carrying out their work.

2 - the need to develop mechanisms to strengthen the process of organizational learning, and to achieve this recommendation must be adopted the following strategies:

Work on the development of a set of training programs related to organizational learning that promotes a culture of collective learning and teamwork.

B - Develop a comprehensive strategy for the adoption of elements of the Organization, which takes into account the strategic, organizational and cultural dimension of this process to enable the application of best practices for learning so that public institutions become educated organizations.

C - Holding conferences and courses that contribute to the consolidation of the concept of an educated organization to increase administrative awareness of this concept.

3 The researcher recommends enhancing the process of participation in decision-making as a means of continuous improvement and improvement of government works, and this is reflected in the benefit of the excellence of subordinates.

4 - Commitment to achieve excellence through the attention to creativity and innovation as a means of doing business and work continuously to update the vision and in line with environmental developments.

5. Encourage employees and motivate them to share knowledge, share information and develop systems that support this process .

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